

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS, CHALLENGES, AND THE RELEVANCE OF ENHANCING EFFECTIVENESS THROUGH DIGITALIZATION IN MANAGING THE ACTIVITIES OF INVESTIGATIVE UNITS OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the relevance of managing the activities of investigative units of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The scientific and practical significance of the topic is related to the digital transformation processes approved by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-155 dated April 30, 2025 "On Comprehensive Measures for the Digital Transformation of the Internal Affairs Bodies System," and the need to increase the effectiveness of combating crime. The article also analyzes the legal basis for managing the activities of investigative units of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, existing problems, and the relevance of increasing efficiency through digitalization. Considering the legislative framework and shortcomings in practice, the importance of implementing foreign experience (digital investigation systems in the USA, Russia, and EU countries) into Uzbekistan's legislation is emphasized. Substantiated proposals are made on the importance of digitalization, including ensuring efficiency, transparency, and integration.

Keywords: Internal Affairs bodies; investigative units; legal framework; digitalization; crime; cybercrime; artificial intelligence; investigation deadlines; effectiveness; digital transformation.

The article also analyzes the legal basis for managing the activities of investigative units of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, existing problems, and the relevance of increasing efficiency through digitalization. Considering the legislative framework and shortcomings in practice, the importance of introducing foreign experience (digital investigation systems in the USA, Russia, and EU countries) into the legislation of Uzbekistan is emphasized.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, within the framework of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," the radical reform of law enforcement agencies, including increasing the effectiveness of investigative units of internal affairs bodies, has become one of the pressing issues. The activities of investigative units of internal affairs bodies play an important role in ensuring public safety. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, investigative bodies play a key role in combating crime, maintaining public order, and protecting citizens' rights. However, in modern conditions, especially against the backdrop of developing digital technologies, the legal basis and challenges of managing investigative activities require adaptation to new requirements. The relevance of increasing efficiency through digitalization has become a global trend, as this process accelerates investigations, reduces errors,

and ensures transparency. The activities of investigative units of internal affairs bodies play an important role in ensuring public safety. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, investigative bodies play a key role in combating crime, maintaining public order, and protecting citizens'

rights. However, in modern conditions, especially against the backdrop of the development of digital technologies, the legal basis and problems of managing investigative activities require adaptation to new requirements.

As a result of increasingly complex crime and the sharp rise in cybercrime, citizens suffered losses of more than 1.9 trillion soums in 2025. Additionally, the requirements of procedural legality and protection of citizens' rights demand that investigative processes be equipped with modern management mechanisms. Managing the activities of investigative units is not only about solving crimes but also about ensuring the procedural independence of investigators, effective distribution of resources, and strengthening monitoring.

Digitalization is bringing about revolutionary changes in this area. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-155 dated April 30, 2025 "On Comprehensive Measures for the Digital Transformation of the System of Internal Affairs Bodies" provides for the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI), Big Data, predictive analytics, and unified information systems in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in 2025-2027. This process will radically change the management of investigative units, allowing for the prediction of crimes and reducing investigation time.

When scientists assess the importance of the topic, some view the improvement of the management system through innovative projects and information support, which increases public trust. Some scholars emphasize adapting the recording of digital evidence to global standards during the investigation process, as this reduces deadlines and prevents legal violations. Other scholars consider the legal framework to be the main factor in creating a people-oriented system, deeming the introduction of digital technologies necessary.

To reduce the time for collecting evidence and conducting investigations in criminal cases, based on Presidential Decree No. PP-105 dated 28.01.2022 "On Measures to Introduce a Unified System of Interdepartmental Electronic Interaction in Pre-trial Proceedings," investigative processes have been automated with the introduction of a unified information system and electronic document management. Some scholars emphasize adapting the recording of digital evidence to global standards during the investigation process, as this reduces deadlines and prevents legal violations.

In order to reduce the time for collecting evidence and conducting investigations in criminal cases, based on Presidential Decree No. PP-105 dated 28.01.2022 "On Measures to Introduce a Unified System of Interdepartmental Electronic Interaction in Pre-trial Proceedings," investigative processes have been automated with the introduction of a unified information system and electronic document management.

For example, for business inquiries, answers are received electronically within seconds, without spending days, weeks, or even months as before. The time of investigative unit personnel is saved, which contributes to the timely consideration of the case. In the future, by improving work in this direction, evidence, video, photographs, 3D scans taken from the crime scene will be immediately uploaded to a single database and automatically analyzed by AI, which will allow identification of a person by facial recognition. Investigators' reports, interrogation protocols, and expert opinions will be maintained electronically - this will reduce the time spent working with paper documents by 40-60%.

As a result of the analysis, due to the digitalization of the sphere, the term of investigation of criminal cases in the investigative unit was reduced on average from 45 to 18-25 days. The

reason for this is: with the help of AI, suspicious individuals were found faster, evidence was automatically linked, and the exchange of information with the prosecutor's office was accelerated.

Analysis of legislation shows that the activities of investigative units of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan are regulated by a number of regulatory legal acts. The Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies" defines the tasks of investigative bodies, which are the detection, investigation, inquiry, and ensuring the legality of crimes.

The Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan regulates the procedural foundations of the investigative process, including pre-investigation verification, collection of evidence, and transfer of the case to the court.

Presidential Decree No. PP-2898 "On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Sphere of Crime Investigation" introduces mechanisms for improving the qualifications and effectiveness of investigative officers. At the same time, Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 727 "On Further Increasing the Effectiveness of Investigating and Solving Crimes by Employees of Investigative Units of Internal Affairs Bodies" defines the procedure for assigning a special qualification class to employees of investigative units.

The Investigative Department under the Ministry of Internal Affairs performs the functions of coordinating, recording, and forming a database of investigative activities. However, contradictions in legislation, such as procedural actions

and the integration of operational-search activities, which creates problems in practice. Also, within the framework of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, documents regulating digitalization, including comprehensive measures for the digital transformation of the internal affairs bodies system, define a unified management mechanism and integration, but the issues of infrastructure and personnel training in their implementation have not been resolved.

First of all, insufficient qualification of personnel, taking into account

Due to the manual nature of the analysis process, the investigation period is extended. Secondly, digitalization in the 102 service and operational control centers has not yet been fully implemented, which leads to data delays and errors. Thirdly, the increase in cybercrimes creates new difficulties in the investigation, since traditional methods are insufficient. The relevance of digitalization lies in the fact that it automates the investigation, integrates databases, and ensures transparency, as a result of which the effectiveness of crime detection increases.

Foreign experience offers valuable lessons in this regard. For example, in the USA, the FBI's Integrated Automated Fingerprint Identification System (IAFIS) and digital forensics systems have accelerated investigations and automated evidence collection. In Russia, police investigations through the "Gosuslugi" portal have been integrated into digital platforms, which has reduced the administrative burden. In the countries of the European Union (for example, Germany and Great Britain), e-police systems have been implemented, which are used to prevent crimes and predict investigations based on AI. It is important to reflect this experience in the legislation of Uzbekistan, as it corresponds to the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" strategy and brings the internal affairs system closer to global standards.

In this direction, it is necessary to include articles regulating digital evidence and electronic investigation in the Criminal Procedure Code; secondly, based on foreign experience, it is necessary to create a single digital platform (for example, an integrated database, as in the USA) and train law enforcement officers; thirdly, to ensure prompt response and information exchange through the full digitalization of the 102 service; fourthly, it is necessary to create special units for cybercrime and strengthen foreign cooperation. Implementation of these measures will increase the effectiveness of the investigation.

It can increase by 20-30%.

By Resolution PQ-155 of 2025, the Department of Digital Technologies and Legal Statistics is being created, and "digital teams" are being formed. This ensures a unified technological approach and accelerates the exchange of information.

The article conducted research based on the analysis of regulatory legal acts, statistical data (obtained from stat.uz and tergov.uz websites) and the opinions of scientists. Methods of analysis: legal analysis, statistical comparison, and identification of problems using practical examples were used.

As a result of the analysis, it became known that a number of problems remain in the activities of investigative units, including the extension of investigation deadlines and procedural violations. Many criminal cases are dragging on, which leads to violations of citizens' rights.

For example, in 2024-2025, cases of extension of investigation deadlines have increased. The number of registered crimes in 2024 amounted to 132,298,

Compared to 2023, it increased by +27.1%, which dramatically increased the investigation load. In 2024, more than 78 thousand criminal cases were considered in courts, and in 2020

This is 2 times more than 38 thousand. In the first half of 2025, 38.5 thousand jobs were registered. This leads to an extension of the investigation period.

While the number of serious crimes has decreased in 2025, cybercrime and the growth in the number of complex economic crimes is prolonging the investigation period, where it is difficult to gather evidence, and forensic examinations are lengthy. According to the Investigative Department, in high-profile cases, for example, cases involving fraud and theft groups, the investigation lasted more than 6-12 months. For example, in Tashkent and the regions, some cases of fraud (cybercrime) last an average of 8-14 months, because evidence, banking transactions,

The collection of IP addresses and international requests is taking a long time.

The main reasons for the problems are:

firstly, the increase in workload - the number of crimes has increased by 113% since 2020, and the number of investigators is insufficient;

secondly, difficulties in gathering evidence - cybercrimes, for economic crimes, expertise and international cooperation are required;

thirdly, cases are returned from the court due to procedural violations - illegal obtaining of evidence, untimely extension of deadlines;

fourthly, the issue of personnel - the qualifications of investigators are insufficient, which prolongs the process.

It is the reforms of 2025, digitalization PQ-155, and the introduction of the investigating judge that are aimed at shortening the deadlines. The introduction of AI and a unified database will contribute to the rapid collection of evidence; strengthening judicial control can reduce procedural violations.

However, in 2025-2026, these changes have not yet yielded full results: instead of decreasing in official statistics, time extensions are being "legally" extended through court. The increase in cases of extending investigative deadlines in 2024-2025 is associated with an increase in the number of crimes, types of complex crimes, and a shortage of investigative resources. This increases the risk of violating citizens' rights. Digitalization and strengthening of judicial control are the main directions for solving this problem, but the results will be more pronounced in 2026-2027.

In 2025, citizens suffered losses of almost 1.9 trillion soums as a result of cybercrimes, and more than 16 thousand cases were registered in the capital. Traditional investigative methods are insufficient for the rapid detection of such crimes. Lack of personnel qualifications: investigators lack sufficient skills in working with AI and digital tools, which affects the quality of the investigation. Poor information exchange: data is exchanged manually between various agencies - the prosecutor's office, the court, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, which leads to delays.

The priority areas defined by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-155 bring the management of investigative units to a new level: the introduction of a unified information system and AI - a database of crimes, predictive analytics, and an automated monitoring system. For example, crime can be prevented by analyzing the criminogenic situation in real time; electronic document management - maintaining documents in electronic form during the investigation process can reduce time by 30-50%. The prosecutor's office also plans to digitize; the use of digital forensic tools - 3D scanning, video analytics, and evidence analysis based on artificial intelligence - will improve the quality of the investigation; "digital teams" and advanced training - highly qualified specialists are involved, special training programs on AI are organized for investigators.

In conclusion, it can be said that the relevance of managing the activities of investigative units of internal affairs bodies is increasing even more in the context of digital transformation. Improvement of legal mechanisms, elimination of problems, and implementation of AI technologies based on the provisions of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-155 and the norms of the Criminal Procedure Code can significantly increase the effectiveness of the fight against crime. The study shows that digitalization requires not only technical, but also legal and organizational reforms. The development of scientific works and regulatory proposals in this area is an urgent task

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